

EVALUATION OF TEACHERS' COMPETENCY IN HIGHER EDUCATION: THE CASE OF EVALUATION BY STUDENTS IN ARBA MINCH UNIVERSITY, ETHIOPIA

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Abstract:

This study aims to investigate the teachers' competency as evaluated by students in Arba Minch University. To this effect, the study identified four main categories to measure teachers' competencies; subject matter knowledge, professional skill, ethical quality, and time management. Descriptive survey type of mixed-method design was used. Institute of Technology and the College of Business and Economics were selected from two institutes, five colleges, and four schools in the university through stratified sampling. Stratification was made based on natural and social science fields. A two-stage simple random sampling technique was used to select 947 undergraduate students with their respective 32 teachers from the selected Institute and College. Data were gathered through the harmonized instructor's performance evaluation scale, which was developed by the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the country. For the analysis of data; mean, standard deviation, independent sample t-test, and bar graph were employed. The analysis has shown that the results of teachers as evaluated by students were moderate in subject matter knowledge, professional skill, and time management competencies. Whereas, in ethical quality it was found to be high. Technology Institute teachers' competency was comparatively higher than the competency of teachers from the College of Business and Economics. Further, it was found that the competency of teachers from the Institute of Technology significantly differs from the competency of teachers from College of Business and Economics with respect to subject matter knowledge, professional skills, and ethical quality. However, the mean score of time management for teachers of the Institute was (3.59±1.18), while for the College teachers it was (3.63±1.17)

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but this difference was statistically not significant ($t = -.538$, $p = .59$). The result has also shown that the major students' feedbacks related to the strength and issues to be improved by teachers in line with the four areas of competencies. Therefore, teachers who evaluated as below average and average levels should use this input to improve their teaching practice and the university should give special emphasis to improve teachers' average levels of competencies through instructional skill and higher diploma program trainings.

Keywords: teachers' competency, students' evaluation, higher education

1. Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

In present times, teachers' performance evaluation is indispensable to meet the teaching-learning standards of an institution. Appraised and rewarded teachers perform better than other counterparts because it creates motivation and urges for performing better. If teachers are motivated, they will produce effective learning of students which is the ultimate goal of an educational institution [12]. To achieve this goal, educational institutions, such as colleges and universities have invested time, personnel, and money to the evaluation process of teachers. Administrative-heads, teachers/colleagues, and students are commonly used as evaluators of teachers' performance in most of the higher education institutions. [15] stated that the evaluation of teachers by students is the most common and controversial method. This method is commonly used in most universities despite controversy over its validity.

Students' ratings of their teacher performance are widely used in higher education institutions to evaluate teaching effectiveness and education quality. Using these rating scales, students rate their teachers' knowledge of the subject matter, enthusiasm and organization, and presentation of the lesson. It is argued that student evaluation rating scales should also address students' evaluation of their own learning experiences in addition to the facilitation role of the teacher. Ratings by all students who took the course are aggregated to form average ratings that are used as feedback to teachers to improve their teaching effectiveness. This evaluation is important as feedback to students, teachers, departments, university administrators, governmental policymakers, and researchers [15].

According to [33], a brief overview of student evaluation of college teaching effectiveness includes a wide range of variables related to the course in general, as well as to the course instructor characteristics and student personality. [18] recognized that student evaluation of teaching primarily focuses on two main areas such as students' perceptions regarding their teachers' performance in class and students' perceptions about teaching effectiveness and quality. A study conducted by [22] examined students' evaluations of teaching effectiveness as a means of enhancing university teaching. [30] investigated how students weigh various teaching components in arriving at their overall

evaluation of teaching effectiveness. [20] also conducted a study on “evaluation of teacher effectiveness through student rating” and suggests that there is a need for implementing student rating as a policy indicator for evaluation of teacher effectiveness. Another study by [7] suggested that student ratings are a necessary source of evidence of teaching effectiveness for both formative and summative decisions and evaluations given by students are an essential component of any evaluation system for teachers. Therefore, acquiring information on students' evaluation of their teachers' effectiveness on teaching provides an additional source of data in the continuous effort to improve effectiveness of teaching.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The major purpose of teachers' evaluation is the improvement of education quality, collection of data for programming, encouraging teachers, supporting teacher's promotion, improvement of the teaching program, and fulfillment of the students' learning needs. Evaluation of coursework and teaching methods are an essential part of the educational process aiming at improving the quality of education. The results of such evaluations are then incorporated into the coursework. Providing feedback to teachers based on evaluation results helps to improve teacher's knowledge about the quality of education. Again, the teacher's knowledge of the essential components of quality of educational performance is a necessary part of teaching [25].

[5] stated that the evaluation of teachers by students could be a key component of educational performance for quality improvement of the teaching methods. Therefore, it is necessary to have a system continuous and formative evaluation of the faculty by students and it is also suggested that assessment of these results could lead to immediate change to improve teaching methods, learning, and educational performance. Evaluations by students and colleagues' faculty have been routinely used in academic institutions and have long been an integral part of the working process of colleges and universities in driving curricular change and teacher's performance [17].

As to ample experience of the present researchers in the study area, evaluation of teachers' teaching effectiveness is undertaken by three bodies, that is, 30% by the head of the department, 20% by colleague teachers, and 50% by students. Regarding the tool used by these three different evaluators to measure the competency of teachers, as a general standard, there are four areas of competency in the revised teachers' performance evaluation checklist which have been used by all evaluators independently. In this contextualized rating scale to evaluate the effectiveness of teachers by students, there are four major competencies, namely; knowledge of the subject matter, professional skill, ethical quality, and time management. Among these four, the knowledge of subject matter is considered as a core competence.

Moreover, as to the view of the present researchers on the study area and information obtained from the review of related studies, it was imagined and understandable that students are the main beneficiary of teacher's quality educational services and they are legitimate individuals to evaluate teacher's competency up to 50%.

That is, feedback to teachers from students' evaluation enables teachers to point out the aspects of teaching activity to be improved and thereby to implement more effective teaching practices. Since students are the main beneficiaries of the improvement in teachers' teaching competency, it seems highly useful to investigate a situation of students' evaluations of teachers' competency in higher education teaching. Through the present study, it has been tried to find out the teachers' level of competency by using students' evaluation in selected departments and faculties of Arba Minch University. Along with this, it has been also tried to find out the teachers' competency difference between an Institute of Technology and the College of Business and Economics with respect to the four categories of competencies. This is very relevant and significant as it will help to know and to take action on the improvement of teachers' level of competency in specific competency levels and helps to compare teaching effectiveness among different institutes and colleges in the University. Therefore, this study intends to investigate the teachers' teaching competency as evaluated by students in order to suggest improvement actions that need to be taken in Arba Minch University.

1.3 Basic Research Question

This study was intended to answer the following basic research questions:

- 1) What is the level of teachers' competency from the students' evaluation?
- 2) Is there a significant difference in teachers' competency among institutes/colleges as evaluated by students?
- 3) What are teachers' strengths and issues that need to be improved based on students' evaluation?

1.4 Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study was to explore the effectiveness of evaluation of teachers' competency by students with regard to the four major areas of teaching competencies in Arba Minch University.

Specific objectives of the study were to:

- 1) determine teachers' level of competency by using student's evaluation.
- 2) identify whether there is a difference in teachers' teaching competency among institute/college as evaluated by students.
- 3) identify teacher's strengths and issues that need to be improved based on students' response.

1.5 Significance of the Study

Since the study addressed unresearched title in the study area focusing on components of teaching competency, it will have the following significance:

- 1) create awareness for academic administrators and teachers about the status of teachers' status in various components of teaching competency as evaluated by students.

- 2) provide a baseline evidence to institutional quality enhancement directorate to organize capacity building short term training for teachers.
- 3) serve as a springboard for further research on the issue under discussion.

1.6 Delimitation of the Study

This study was confined to evaluate teachers' competency by students in Arba Minch University. Conceptually, the research was delimited to investigate the practices of teachers' competency evaluation by students in terms of the four dimensions which are already identified by the Ministry of Science and Higher Education such as knowledge of the subject matter, professional skill, ethical quality, and time management competency. Teacher evaluation by the head of departments and colleagues are out of the scope of this study.

2. Literature Review

The evaluation of teaching performance in higher education is the only one that involves students in the role of evaluators. Students are not supervisors of the teacher, but there are already many higher education institutions that ask students to evaluate each teacher for each course and each semester [9][8][27]. Students' evaluations of teacher competencies and performance are one of the main tools for assessing the quality of university education [23][24]. This need for evaluation has received increasing public attention, as the number of people attending higher education is increasing, and this depends more and more on scarce resources. In this sense, the evaluation of the quality of teachers by the students is one of the crucial components of the evaluation of the quality of teaching (together with the external evaluation and evaluation of heads and peers) and the so-called teacher accountability [16].

The evaluation of competency of teachers by the students is important to inquire about the quality of the educational process in a university since the evaluation of teacher's performance by students allows to obtain objective information on the performance of the teacher, it makes possible to determine the level of conformity between their practices and the goals and tasks of a university, as well as the needs of the students. There are authors who highlight the added value of student involvement in the process of assessing the quality of teaching, taking into account the benefits in terms of their satisfaction, participation, and current expectations [31]. On the other hand, students' evaluations on teaching are one of the main tools to evaluate university teaching and the work of teachers, in terms of pedagogical, technical and overall quality of teaching, thereby influencing teacher career management and the professional development of teachers in higher education [11][23].

According to [14] the different forms of teacher evaluation in higher education can focus on the individual performance of teachers in classrooms (teacher praise/distinction, peer evaluation, and student ratings); in the evaluation of school context performance (external inspection and internal self-assessment of the school) and in the assessment of

student outcomes (national and regional student assessments and value-added assessments to measure learning gains over time). The instruments for assessing the quality of teaching at the institutional level can be divided into three groups: organizational (self-examination university and teacher classifications), pedagogical (instruments to assess student achievement achievements), sociological and customer satisfaction monitoring (that is the evaluation of the quality of the teachers by the students). There is, however, little consensus on how to adequately measure teacher quality, especially in higher education, where the availability of standardized tests to analyze performance is still scarce.

Furthermore, [3] in their book entitled "Handbook for Teaching Competence Enhancement in Higher Education" listed the major higher education teachers' competence areas for teaching as; mastery of academic discipline in service of the teaching process, professionalism and professional development of higher education teachers, curriculum planning and development in higher education, learning and students, planning, organizing, and implementing the teaching process, assessment and self-assessment of student achievements, mentoring, application of new technologies in teaching, and communication and social skills.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

In undertaking this study, a descriptive survey design of mixed-method research was employed. The survey was chosen to explore the status of teachers' competency by using students' evaluations and to identify the difference in competency of teachers among institutes/colleges. Since qualitative data was there, an explanatory design was used to build upon and explain the initial quantitative results [13]. Moreover, the study described the feedback of students while evaluating their teachers' competency and addressed their strength and issues need to be improved.

3.2 Description of the Study Area

Arba Minch University is one of the biggest and pioneers public higher learning institutions in Ethiopia, which is located at Arba Minch town, 500 km south of Addis Ababa, capital of the country. Currently, the university has six campuses with 6 colleges, 2 institutes, and 4 schools with 146 Graduate Assistant Instructors, 714 lecturers, 120 Assistance Professors, 14 Associate Professors and 1 professor. In various programs at undergraduate and graduate level the university has totally above 37,400 students in the academic year of 2018/19. As one of the first-generation University of the country, it has undergone organizational structural reform that would enable to provide efficient and effective services for a decade by implementing different transforming modalities.

3.3 Population and Sampling of the Study

The target population of this study was all undergraduate regular students and their teachers of Arba Minch University and samples were selected from these groups in the 2018/19 academic year. An Institute of Technology from Natural Sciences and College of Business and Economics from social sciences were selected by using a stratified sampling technique from the strata of natural sciences and social sciences fields. By using simple random technique two departments out of four from the College of Business and Economics and two faculties out of five from the Institute of Technology were selected. Likewise, 16 teachers out of 34 with their 542 students from the Accounting and Finance and Economics departments and again 16 teachers out of 37 with their 405 students from Civil Engineering and Electrical and Computer Engineering Faculties were selected randomly. Therefore, as indicated in Table 1 below, the study sample consisted of 947 (males 608 and females 339) 1st to 3rd-year undergraduate regular students and their respective 32 (males 27 and females 5) teachers of the Institute and College.

Table 1: Description of Study Participants

College/Institute and Department/Faculty		Batch	Participant Students			Participant Teachers		
			M	F	T	M	F	T
College of Business and Economics	Economics	Year I	127	63	190	3	-	3
		Year II	112	89	201	4	1	5
	Accounting and Finance	Year II	46	44	90	3	2	5
		Year III	33	28	61	3	-	3
Institute of Technology	Civil Engineering	Year I	87	38	125	4	-	4
		Year III	98	22	120	3	1	4
	Electrical and Computer Engineering	Year II	45	18	63	4	1	5
		Year III	60	37	97	3	-	3
Total			608	339	947	27	5	32

3.4 Data Collection Instrument

Instructors Performance Evaluation Scale to be filled by students which was a harmonized tool developed by the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of Ethiopia was employed. This scale consisted of 19 items which were grouped into four categories of competencies, namely; knowledge of the subject matter, professional skill, ethical quality, and time management. The items were a Likert type scale with a scoring range between 1 and 5 points, which correspond as 1 (very low), 2 (low), 3 (average), 4 (high), 5 (very high), and NA (not applicable). Moreover, to collect qualitative data related to the teachers' strength and issues need to be improved the evaluation checklist has two open-ended questions.

3.5 Data Collection Procedures

At the beginning, students were informed about this evaluation of their teachers' competency was only for research purpose. In order to evaluate the four competencies of

teachers an evaluation scale was carried out in paper format, and with which the students evaluated their respective teachers, through a set of five items that focused on the subject matter competency; eight items related to professional skill; four items that evaluated ethical quality competency and two items that evaluated time management. To reduce rating bias, students provided the ratings before they knew their course grades, that is, two weeks before the final examination. The evaluations were done, without the presence of the instructors, and the students were informed that the instructors would not be permitted to see the results. The mean values of the student ratings of teaching were used for analysis purposes.

3.6 Data Analysis Method

The data collected from sample students via the scale were manually entered into the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 20.0 software program for data analysis. Descriptive statistics mean and standard deviation were used to examine the rating of the respondents based on the level of competencies and an independent sample t-test was used to find out any significant differences between natural sciences and social sciences in teachers' competencies using students' evaluation. The data collected through open-ended questions were presented and analyzed using the content analysis technique.

4. Results and Discussion

The purpose of the present study is to explore the level of teachers' competency by using students' evaluation. In order to show the level of competencies, based on the Likert scale, the continuous values of the average evaluation were transformed into categorical variables: the first category "very low" integrated the evaluations in the range of (1-2), the second category "low" included the evaluations in the range (2-3), the third category "average" included the assessments in the range (3-4), the fourth category "high" included the evaluations in the range (4-5), and the fifth category ("very high") included evaluations with values equal to (5). Also, students' responses on their teachers' strengths and issues need to be improved were described and t-ratios were calculated to test the difference between natural sciences and social sciences teachers on the four categories of competency.

4.1 Teachers' Level of Competency by Using Students' Evaluation

Under this section, the descriptive statistics, mean and standard deviation were used to show the teachers' level of competency at departments and faculties level and also tried to show the overall competency evaluation result in both natural and social sciences teachers of the university.

As the study revealed from the College of Business and Economics, the evaluation result of three teachers by freshman students' from the Department of Economics showed that the mean was found an average in all four areas of competencies; knowledge of

subject matter (M=3.43, SD=1.08), professional skill (M=3.17, SD=1.14), ethical quality (M=3.73, SD=1.11), and time management (M=3.48, SD=1.24). The other five teachers from the same department were evaluated by year two students and the evaluation result indicated that on the competency of knowledge of subject matter (M=4.01, SD=.76) and ethical quality (M=4.31, SD=.89) competencies were high and the remains professional skill (M=3.58, SD=.98) and time management (M=3.80, SD=.95) were computed as average level.

Also, eight teachers were evaluated from Department of Accounting and Finance in the college understudy; the descriptive statistics of five teachers who evaluated by year two students with respect to knowledge of the subject matter competency (M=3.36, SD=1.28), professional skill (M=3.61, SD=1.09), and time management (M=3.58, SD=1.39) were average and their evaluation of ethical quality (M=4.36, SD=.73) competency was high level. Likewise, three teachers' competency evaluation by year three students from the same department were labeled as average in the knowledge of subject matter (M=3.17, SD=1.25), professional skill (M=3.06, SD=1.15) and time management (M=3.63, SD=1.19) competencies. With ethical quality competency (M=4.16, SD=.96), their evaluation result was scored high level.

On the other hand, the study also revealed the students' evaluation result of teachers' level of competencies in two faculties of the Institute of Technology. According to first-year students' evaluation of four teachers, competency from faculty of Civil Engineering indicated that the mean values obtained for each set of competencies; knowledge of subject matter (M=4.25, SD=.54), professional skill (M=4.24, SD=.59), ethical quality (M=4.56, SD=.76), and time management (M=4.04, SD=.94) which were categorized as the high level of competency. From the same faculty, the other four teachers also evaluated their teaching effectiveness by year three students. Their mean evaluation result on the knowledge of the subject matter (M=4.28, SD=.50) and ethical quality (M=4.43, SD=.72) competency was high and the evaluation result of professional skill (M=3.98, SD=.96) and time management (M=3.78, SD=1.21) competencies was computed as an average, which was very close to a high level.

Similarly, evaluation of teachers competency was done in faculty of Electrical and Computer Engineering in the Institute; the result of five teachers competency evaluation by year two students revealed that mean values with time management competency (M=2.51, SD=1.00) was low and on the other two competencies evaluation knowledge of subject matter (M=3.46, SD=.87) and professional skill (M=3.30, SD=.74) were leveled as average. Whereas, the mean of the ethical quality competency (M=4.02, SD=.84) was scored a high level. The other three teachers were evaluated from the same department by year three students and their evaluation result failed on an average level on the four areas of competency; knowledge of subject matter (M=3.22, SD=.91), professional skill (M=3.39, SD=.85), ethical quality (M=3.87, SD=.78) and time management (M=3.47, SD=1.08) competencies.

Table 2: Teachers' average level of competency
 in Institute of Technology and College of Business and Economics

Area of Competency	No of Students	No of Teachers	Min.	Max.	M	SD
Subject matter knowledge	947	32	1.00	5.00	3.73	.995
Professional skill	947	32	1.00	5.00	3.57	.979
Ethical quality	947	32	1.00	5.00	4.17	.928
Time management	947	32	1.00	5.00	3.62	1.174
Grand mean	947	32	1.00	5.00	3.77	.864

Note: Min=Minimum; Max=Maximum; M=Mean and SD=Standard Deviation

As shown in Table 2, the result revealed that the overall teachers level of competencies in both Institute of Technology and College of Business and Economics were average with results for subject matter knowledge competency (M=3.73, SD=.995), professional skill competency (M=3.57, SD=.979), and time management competency (M=3.62, SD=1.174). Whereas, student's evaluation of their teacher's ethical quality competency (M=4.17, SD=.928) was a high level. The scores attributed by the students in each item of competencies revealed an equal dispersion of data between 1 (minimum) and 5 (maximum) points, that is, rankings between very low and very high, respectively.

In the present study, it is found that the evaluation of teachers' competency by students in both Institute and College was ranged between an average or satisfactory to high-level categorization since the majority of classifications of competencies as well as the overall mean were leveled as an average and the ethical quality competency of teachers was the one that registered a greater oscillated evaluation mean scored by students. In supporting the importance of the students' evaluation of teachers competency [11][23] stressed that students' evaluations on teaching are one of the main tools to evaluate university teaching and the work of teachers, in terms of pedagogical, technical and overall quality of teaching, thereby influencing teacher career management and the professional development of teachers in higher education. The outcome of this study is similar to a study conducted by [1], entitled "the evaluation of teachers' competencies in the Higher Education of East Timor: Students Perspective". The finding revealed that the average of the evaluations of pedagogical, professional, social, and teacher competencies ranged from (3) "sufficient" and (4) "good". In analyzing how students measured and evaluated the competences of public higher education university teachers, it was possible to conclude about the quality of the performance of this teaching system in East Timor, although it is worth pointing out some improvements resulting from the students' evaluation of the various dimensions of teachers' performance. Moreover, a study on "Teacher Effectiveness of College Teachers" also revealed that the majority of college teachers are effective only at a moderate level. It is also found that the management or nature of the institutions has a significant influence on various dimensions of teacher effectiveness [4].

4.2 Differences in Teacher Competencies Between Natural and Social Sciences

Under this section, the differences in the evaluation of teachers' competencies by students in the Institute of Technology and the College of Business and Economics were identified by comparing the means of the two groups. To this effect, an independent samples t-test was computed to see whether there exists a significant difference in the evaluation of teachers' competencies between an institute and a college.

Table 3: Differences in teachers' competencies between
 Institute of Technology and College of Business and Economics

Area of Competency	Institute of Technology		College of Business and Economics		Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	t-value
	M	SD	M	SD			
Subject matter knowledge	3.89	.838	3.61	1.083	.287	.065	4.437*
Professional skill	3.81	.809	3.38	.809	.431	.063	6.856*
Ethical quality	4.27	.818	4.10	.997	.172	.061	2.834*
Time management	3.59	1.179	3.63	1.171	-.415	.077	-.538

Note: N=947 (IoT=405 & CBE=542) and *significant at the 0.01 level(2-tailed)

As presented in Table 3, there was a significant difference between the Institute of Technology and the College of Business and Economics regarding the first three competencies of teachers using student evaluation. Results revealed that core competency, which is subject matter knowledge for teachers of Institute (M=3.89, SD=.838) is high in comparison to teachers of a College (M=3.61, SD=1.083). Similarly, teachers of Technology Institute (M=3.81, SD=.809) are more effective in professional skill competency as compared to teachers of a College (M=3.38, SD=.809). Scores of ethical quality competencies for teachers of Technology Institute (M=4.27, SD=.818) is higher in comparison to teachers of a College (M=4.10, SD=.997). Whereas, the findings revealed there is no significant difference found in the scores of time management competency between the Institute of Technology and the College of Business and Economics.

Therefore, the findings of this study also demonstrated that by students evaluation the competencies of teachers from faculties of Civil Engineering, and Electrical and Computer Engineering in the Institute of Technology were higher in comparison to teachers from Economics, and Accounting and Finance departments in College of Business and Economics in the majority of competencies; knowledge of the subject matter, professional skill, and ethical quality.

Figure 1: The Difference in average Teachers' competency between the Institute of Technology and the College of Business and Economics

Likewise, as can easily be seen in Figure 1, except for the time management competency, there is a significant difference between teachers' competency in an Institute of Technology and a College of Business and Economics from the perspective of students' evaluation of their teachers' subject matter knowledge, professional skill, and ethical quality competencies. In relation to this, a study conducted by [28] found that there is variation by discipline in students' beliefs as to what constitutes 'good teaching'. [6] also found that laboratory courses rate higher than lectures or tutorials. While it is understandable that active hands-on learning would be preferred by many students, issues arise when these students' evaluations of teaching effectiveness scores are used for summative purposes and to compare instructors across different faculties.

4.3 Major Responses of Students on their Teachers Strength and Issues Need to be Improved

Receiving feedback from students has become the most common source in higher education in the evaluation of teaching. Based on the final open-ended question, the respondent students gave their responses to their teachers' competency strengths and aspects that need to be improved. Of the 947 respondents of the questionnaire, 578 (61%) students provided comments to the open-ended question. Hereunder the students' major feedbacks about their teachers' strengths and suggestions on the issues need to improve were presented in a categorized manner based on the area of competencies.

Based on this category, the major responses of students regarding the strength of their teachers from Institute of Technology and College of Business and Economics were described in line with the competencies; students' responses related to their teachers' strength on subject matter knowledge competency showed that majority of teachers have knowledge of the course, skill to prepare appropriate teaching material, skill to construct

tests and final exam, and they are good in presentation as well as preparation. Similarly, about professional skill competency students raised about their teachers' strong side on communication, using appropriate teaching methods, maintaining strong relationship/approaches, giving practical and related examples, using appropriate teaching materials, encouraging group learning with close follow up, giving a tutorial class for females and needy students, respect their profession, trying to be model in life, arranging an additional time for practical tasks, and being energetic and cooperative were addressed. Concerning ethical quality competency, respondents mentioned about their teacher's behavior of equal treatment and respect and concern in advising on different issues. Regarding time management competency, the majority of respondents raised their teacher's competency on punctuality, on time course coverage and timely provision of feedback on continuous assessment were the most common.

On the other hand, concerning issues need to be improved on teacher's competency were also revealed by some students from both Institute of Technology and College of Business and Economics, on knowledge of subject matter competency students suggested the improvement of mismatch between the lesson and examination, speaking a lot about personal life, not covering the allotted course content, lack of preparation for daily sessions, frequently using common examples, doing laboratory activities, being very far from the scope of the lesson objectives, and associating the lesson with practical examples were specified. In the same way, respondent students also indicated issues need to give more emphasis to improve by teachers about professional skill competency as; poor teaching and assessment, consideration of students level of understanding in presentation as well as examination, delivery of continuous assessment and scoring, giving tutorial/ makeup class for female and low achievers, unlaudable sound and being speedy in presentation, following participatory approaches, classroom management, poor communication, giving many tasks/exercises at a time. preparation of worksheets and unreadable handwriting. According to respondent student's suggestion to improve the ethical quality competency of their teachers, feeling of anger in silly mistakes, not accepting and respecting others idea, taking mass measure on disciplinary problems, unable to easily understand/consider students' feeling, and aggressiveness were indicated to be improved by teachers. Regarding time management competency late coming and absenteeism from regular classes, wastage of time in simple and specific issues, timely giving continuous assessment and final exam, and its feedback was raised to be considered to improve the time management competency of teachers in both College and an Institute.

In this regard, [6] suggested that in student's evaluation scale it is possible to point out the strengths and /or those that require improvement. [2][32] stressed that students' feedback on teachers' teaching practices enables teachers to reflect on their actions, the adoption of more effective teaching practices, and the attribution of increasing responsibility of students to improve the entire public higher education system. Student evaluation of teaching and, particularly, the written comments make teacher evaluation data more convincing, meaningful, and contribute to the improvement of teaching

accordingly [29]. In the research by [10] revealed the importance of student evaluations and found that students can offer meaningful feedback when they believe and see that their input is being valued. [26][29] also stated that student evaluation can assess only those characteristics that are observable by students, such as covering learning objectives, keeping to teaching hours, fulfilling all teaching hours, speaking clearly, keeping the classroom environment positive for learning, knowing the names of the students, and choosing appropriate materials. It is important to stress that properly designed student surveys can be used as a measure of lecturers' teaching performance. Nevertheless, it should be borne in mind that students cannot make judgments about teachers' performance from all aspects.

5. Conclusion

Students' evaluation of teachers' competency cannot be the sole measure of effective teaching but obtaining student feedback is very useful to improve the teaching quality of teachers. In this study, sampled students from two departments and two faculties have evaluated their teacher's competencies by using the harmonized tool that encompasses knowledge of the subject matter, professional skill, ethical quality, and time management competencies. The results revealed that the overall competency of teachers working in the departments of the College of Business and Economics and faculties of the Institute of Technology was found to be an average level. It means that by students' evaluation teacher's effectiveness on subject matter knowledge, professional skill, and time management competencies were moderate or satisfactory level. Through the present study, it has been proved that students' evaluation of their teacher's ethical competency at both the Institute of Technology and College of Business and Economics level was evaluated as high. The results also indicate that there is a statistically significant difference between the competency of teachers in the Institute of Technology and College of Business and Economics concerning subject matter knowledge, professional skill, and ethical quality competencies. It can be said that according to students' evaluation, teachers of the Institute of Technology are comparatively more effective than the College of Business and Economics in the majority of competencies. Moreover, the study demonstrated that students' evaluation of their teachers' effectiveness by providing feedback on the major teachers' strengths and aspects to be improved in line with the four categories of competencies.

Therefore, it has to be remembered that students' evaluations of teaching effectiveness are used in most universities and colleges throughout the world, and many researchers have analyzed its importance. Based on the finding of this study, the researchers recommended that Arba Minch University should give special emphasis to improve teachers' competencies evaluated as below average and average levels through enhancing instructional skills training. Most importantly, teachers should use this research input to improve their teaching practice and personal quality to achieve better

level of competencies in their teaching. Finally, the researchers suggest further research has to be conducted by including more faculties and departments from the university.

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